

Estimation of the adsorption coefficient of palmitic acid in soil

Authors

Katia Mainolfi

Completion date

April 24, 2024

Sponsor/Project

SafeWax

Performing Facility

Eurofins Agroscience Services Regulatory Germany GmbH
Eutinger Str. 24, 75223 Niefern-Öschelbronn, Germany

Eurofins Agroscience Regulatory Report

S23-101986-06/002

6 pages

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	2
INTRODUCTION	3
RESULTS	3
REFERENCES	3
APPENDIX	4

INTRODUCTION

This report documents the QSAR estimation of the adsorption coefficient (Koc) of palmitic acid in soil was obtained using the Estimation Programs Interface Suite™ (EPI Suite) for Microsoft® Windows by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2012) which includes the Soil Adsorption Coefficient Program for Microsoft Windows (KOCWIN) in version v 2.0. Both estimation methods, based on the experimental log octanol-water partition coefficient (log Kow) and on Molecular Connectivity Index (MCI), were used.

The following information on chemical identity and log Kow (experimental Data Base of EPI Suite) of palmitic acid were entered into the software:

Name: palmitic acid
IUPAC name: hexadecanoic acid
CAS Number: 57-10-3
SMILES : CCCCCCCCCCCCCC(=O)O
Molecular formula: C16 H32 O2
Molecular weight: 256.42
log Kow (experimental DB): 8.23

RESULTS

Estimated (QSAR) Koc for palmitic acid was 13230 L/kg (based on log Kow) or 3522 L/kg (based on MCI), indicating that the substance is slightly mobile to immobile according to McCall et al. (1981) classification.

However, adsorption values should be treated with caution since palmitic acid is a ionisable substance, hence its Koc may be sensitive to soil pH.

REFERENCES

United States Environmental Protection Agency (2012). Estimation Programs Interface Suite™; (EPI Suite) for Microsoft™; Windows Version 4.1. Washington DC, USA.

McCall P.J., Laskowski D.A., Swann R.L., and Dishburger H.J., (1981), "Measurement of sorption coefficients of organic chemicals and their use, in environmental fate analysis", in Test Protocols for Environmental Fate and Movement of Toxicants. Proceedings of AOAC Symposium, AOAC, Washington DC.

